

winters are extremely cold in the hills (temperature often below 0 °C), only a few of the overwintering larvae survive. High infestations are caused mainly by the second generation larvae resulting from the mass egg laying during Jul-Aug. □

Chemical control of rice stem borers (SB) in the Punjab

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Three SB species—*Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens*—damage rice in the Punjab. *S. incertulas* is predominant. Damage has been recorded in rice nurseries in certain pockets of Amritsar, Ferozpur, and Faridkot districts.

SB incidence has increased during the last 2 yr. Staggered sowing over a longer period, an increase in the area under irrigation, growing unapproved susceptible varieties, and other agronomic manipulations appear to be

Effect of different insecticides on incidence of rice SB.^a Punjab, India.

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Incidence (% whiteheads)	Yield (t/ha)
Cartap hydrochloride 4 G	1.5	3.8 a	5.3 a
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	26.4 bed	3.2 d
Carbofuran 3 G	1.0	25.4 bc	4.2 b
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.5	20.2 b	4.2 b
Deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC	0.09	33.3 d	3.1 d
Phosalone 35 EC	0.5	26.1 bed	3.8 c
Control	—	32.3 cd	2.4 e

^aIn a column, values designated by different letters are statistically different (Duncan's multiple range test).

factors in the increase.

Control of SB is with insecticides. We evaluated two new granular compounds, chlorpyrifos 10 G and cartap hydrochloride 4 G, with carbofuran 3 G as the standard. Chlorpyrifos 40 EC, deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC, and phosalone 35 EC as foliar spray also were evaluated.

Recommended variety PR103 was grown in 17-m² plots in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Single applications of chemicals were given the first week of Sep 1986, when the crop was nearly 40 d old and when deadhearts reached 5%.

Among the granular insecticides, cartap hydrochloride was most effective (see table). Average whitehead incidence was only 3.8%, compared to 25.4% with carbofuran and 26.4% with chlorpyrifos 10 G. Foliar application of chlorpyrifos 40 EC showed 20.2% incidence, significantly lower than deltamethrin + buprofezin but statistically equal to phosalone.

The significantly highest yield was with cartap hydrochloride. Cartap hydrochloride 4 G granular insecticide at 1.5 kg ai/ha controlled rice SB and promoted yield. □

Monitoring susceptibility of rice pests to insecticides

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Following FAO/IRRI workshops—“Judicious and Efficient Use of Insecticides on Rice” (1983) and “Monitoring Susceptibility Levels of Rice Pests to Insecticides” (1984)—12

Asian rice-growing countries formed a network to establish baseline insecticide susceptibility of major rice pests.

Susceptibility to insecticides was determined by topical application with the Kiya hand-operated microapplicator and a calibrated microsyringe. A specified volume of insecticides for each test insect was applied on the thoracic tergites (Table 1). Treated insects were transferred through a funnel to minimize mechanical damage to plastic tumbler cages containing 8-10 2-wk-old TN1 seedlings.

Larvae were transferred to petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and provided with cut leaves or diet for stem borer. The tests usually had 3 replications, with at least 15 insects/replication. Cages and petri dishes were kept in an incubator or controlled room at 25-30 °C, 60-80% relative humidity, and 12-h light. Larval

mortality was recorded 24, 48, and 72 h after treatment. LD₅₀/LD₉₅ values of the insecticides were computed using probit analysis.

Five countries have established susceptibility baseline data for *N. lugens* (Table 2). Indonesia had relatively higher LD₅₀ values with three insecticides, indicating that *N. lugens* in Indonesia may be less susceptible to insecticides. However, *N. lugens* from two collection sites did not show much

Table 1. Rice insect pests and volume of insecticides applied.

Insect pest	Volume applied (μl)
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	1.0
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	0.5
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	0.2
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0.1
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	0.1